

THE EFFECTS OF CLIMATE CHANGE ON GLOBAL FOOD SECURITY

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Abstract: Climate change poses significant challenges to global food security, impacting various aspects of food production, distribution, and access. Rising temperatures, changing precipitation patterns, and extreme weather events are disrupting agricultural systems worldwide. These changes affect crop yields, livestock productivity, and fisheries, leading to food shortages, price volatility, and reduced nutritional quality. Additionally, climate change exacerbates existing vulnerabilities, particularly in regions with limited resources and infrastructure. Addressing these challenges requires multifaceted approaches that integrate climate adaptation and mitigation strategies with sustainable agricultural practices and equitable food distribution systems.

Key words: The effects of climate change on global food security are a critical concern. Rising temperatures, changing precipitation patterns, and extreme weather events can all impact crop yields, food production, and distribution systems. Climate change threatens to disrupt food supplies, increase food prices, and exacerbate hunger and malnutrition worldwide. Adaptation strategies, such as crop diversification, improved water management, and sustainable agricultural practices, are crucial for enhancing food security in a changing climate.

The impact of climate change on global food security is likely to be enormous. These changes may affect good crop yields and water resources, changes in food prices, and increased natural disasters (such as the exhumed head buffalo). The impact of variables on food products usually occurs through the price and adaptation of available products. In some cases, changes related to dryness and cleanliness can increase safety, because in these cases, water and its resources fall and are damaged.

Climate change is one of the most important problems of our time. If Twenty years ago, it was discussed only in scientific circles, until today this problem became known to many people. We feel that the temperature is getting warmer and the weather in general is becoming more variable. Let's travel there is no doubt that the climate is changing and this change is happening rapidly. You are one See, in the last 130 years, the average temperature on Earth has risen by 1°C. On a planetary scale, rise in temperature that seems to be very little noticeable at first glance, its inhabitants, plants, It can be dangerous for your animals and us. Besides that, 1°C is it is the world average. Humans are mostly not from the climate, maybe they complain about the weather. "Throughout October, strong winds blew, continuous rains fell. Then very cold, frosty morning, faces and fingers the painful icy windy November has come" (J.Rowling, "Harry Potter and the Phoenix Order"). You see, even literary works are usually about the weather nothing is said about the climate. This can be understood from a human point of view: to know the weather, simply look out the window it is enough to look. We encounter weather every day, and climate is somewhat different is incomprehensible.

Today, almost everyone, including scientists, is talking about its change both politicians and businessmen speak. They often contradict each other express opinions: some say it's good, others say it's bad, others say it's bad and they claim that nothing is happening to the climate. Geographical location of Uzbekistan, distance from oceans and seas, Eurasia the location in the interior of the mainland, the continental climate of the country defines. The climate is continental, the weather is cloudless for most of the year presence, high temperature in summer, low atmospheric precipitation, water in kata evaporation, duration and heat of summer, as well as winter The air temperature is daily and annual due to its coldness, which is not typical for these latitudes is manifested in the size of their amplitudes. This is the climate of Uzbekistan characteristics are formed under the influence of climatic factors. Cold air currents easily penetrates to the southernmost regions of the country, where it is the most in winter small air temperature can drop to -25°C . Northern part of Uzbekistan (Ustyurt Plateau) the absolute minimum temperature value is -39.7°C (1969, February). During the year, high levels of solar radiation flux are great heat creates conditions for the formation of hearths. Central desert of Uzbekistan in summer extreme air temperature in the zones reaches $45-49^{\circ}\text{C}$. On the state of the climate system modern monitoring data throughout Uzbekistan, all year round that the number of days with high air temperature in the seasons is increasing is showing. The highest level of rapid increase in the number of "heat wave" days It is recorded in the area along the island and at the foot of the Amudarya. Climate change droughts, floods, heat waves, floods, avalanches and other such leading to an increase in the frequency of such dangerous events. Wide dangerous natural phenomena, including droughts and heat waves covers large areas and population groups at the same time. On the contrary, flood events such as floods, inundation, landslides, avalanches, etc based on the forming factors, it has a local character. However, climate change resulting in more intense and frequent climate-related hazardous events becomes repetitive.

- This was not the case before. Now the soil is tired and dry," he says Fardinatri. Conflict between economic development and environmental protection can lead to instability in food production, says specialists. Climate change is one of the main problems of the 21st century. Humanity in order to achieve development, to treat nature like a peasant causing environmental imbalance. Climate warming as a result, snow cover is shrinking, evaporation is increasing.

And finally, let's face it, it's the most pressing thing the world faces one of the problems is food. Every year, basically, the world's population is exploding the situation worsens due to growth. At this stage of human evolution one of the most important tasks is to find the best solutions to the food problem. Globalization processes currently taking place in the economy, science and along with technical achievements, the most effective solution to this problem We hope it will help you find it.

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